

Investigation of mechanisms responsible for dimensional variations of composite U-channel and L-shape elements.

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Abstract

The aim of the present research activity is to identify the mechanisms driving the process of deformation in composite elements. An investigation of the thermoelastic behaviour in AS4/8552 composite components has been performed. The effect of arm length on the value of the spring-in angle was studied. Laser measurement equipment was developed and adopted for investigation of thermally induced distortion in a U-shaped component. Finally both arms of the U-channel were slit in several places along the length. It was shown that the constraint effect from neighbouring parts clearly contributes to the geometry of the specimen.

1. Introduction

The application of composite materials in the aerospace industry is growing very rapidly, so the need to obtain reproducible, interchangeable and tightly toleranced manufactured components has become a very important issue.

Before making an attempt to predict and eliminate the dimensional variability in composite components, it is necessary to separate and understand all the factors contributing to the final deformation.

It has been widely discussed in the literature that residual stresses which appear in the laminate due to mismatch of thermal expansion coefficients along and across the plies, chemical shrinkage of the resin, as well as tool-part interaction lead to the final deflection of the component, fig.1.

Fig.1. Deformed shape of an L and U-section element at the end of the curing process.

The residual stresses in polymer composites arise primarily due to the anisotropic thermal expansion of individual plies. The build-up of residual stresses during the cure of composite parts can lead to laminate cracking [1]. The presence of high residual stresses and micro-cracks can affect the performance of the cured part, thus the state of process induced stresses within the composite structure must be known before it is put into service.

The problem of residual stresses/strains and related spring-in effects in L-shaped structures has been treated in the past by several authors.

In their investigation into separating sources of manufacturing distortions, Radford and Rennick [2], manufactured composite angle brackets with varying stacking sequence, laminate thickness, and corner radius. A change of the included angle as a result of temperature excursions was measured using a laser technique. All specimens responded linearly to the applied temperature. It was concluded that the thermoelastic contribution to the final spring-in angle was independent of the laminate thickness and corner radius. The laminate stacking sequence was found to have the biggest effect on the thermoelastic response. It was found that the laminate thickness as well as sample radius contributes to the non-thermoelastic portion of the spring-in.

Numerical studies [3,4,5] show that simple thermoelastic models can not predict the total spring-in angle. A more complex description of the curing cycle and tooling conditions has to be considered.

Research was carried by Fernlund et al. [6] to investigate the factors affecting spring-in and bowing of the arms of L-sections. A number of parameters were found to affect the bowing, including the laminate thickness, the length of the sample arms, cure cycle, the tool material and the tool surface condition.

An RTM technique was used by Svanberg and Holmberg [7] to study the spring-in phenomenon. It was shown that the final geometry of the component depends on the thermal expansion coefficient in the glassy and rubbery state, chemical shrinkage and frozen-in deformations. The cool-down rate did not influence the final value of the spring-in angle.

The aim of the present research activity is to identify all the mechanisms driving the process of deformation in composite elements with single curvature. An experimental investigation of the thermoelastic behaviour in AS4/8552 composite components has been performed. The laser measurement technique presented in [1], was modified and adopted for investigation of thermally induced distortion in U-shaped components. Variation in the value of the initial spring in angle along the length of the U-channel was examined. It was shown that the tool-part interaction has a significant effect on the final geometry of the component.

2. Manufacturing of L-shape and U-channel specimens

2.1 Manufacturing procedure

Both L-shape and U-shape specimens, were prepared on an aluminium female mould. Before starting the laying-up process the mould was cleaned, and two types of release agents were applied:

- Frekote B-15
- Frekote 770-NC

Frekote B-15 is used for covering mould porosity and small surface imperfections. Frekote 770-NC is then applied after 30 minutes time. Each ply of the prepreg was carefully laid-up inside the mould. A vacuum was applied every 4 plies to minimise possible effects of corner bridging. Sides of the sample were dammed with cork, to minimise the effect of resin flow in the in-plane directions. To decrease corner thickening of the sample, the plastic vacuum bag was specially folded as shown in fig.2. It is believed that without this fold the bag can bridge during the curing process, creating additional space for resin.

Fig.2 Cross-section through the mould during curing process 1. aluminium mould, 2. composite sample 3. release film 4. breather 5. nylon bag

2.2 Material

The material used in this study is unidirectional carbon epoxy AS4/8552 composite system. The thickness of a single ply is 0.25 mm. Samples were cured in an autoclave according to the recommended cure cycle provided by the HEXCEL company. The cure cycle is illustrated in figure 3.

Fig. 3 Cure cycle for AS4/8552 composite system

2.3 List of specimens

A number of specimens were prepared as a part of this study. A detailed description of each part is shown in table 1.

Table 1. Geometrical details of the composite specimens

Symbol	description	Stacking sequence	Arm length mm	Length mm	Radius mm
L1	L-section	8 plies [45/90/135/0] _s	25	50	16
L2	L-section	8 plies [45/90/135/0] _s	40	50	16
L3	L-section	8 plies [45/90/135/0] _s	50	50	16
L4	L-section	8 plies [45/90/135/0] _s	70	50	16
UL1	U-channel	16 plies [45/90/135/0/45/0/135/0] _s	60	500	16 and 30

0° direction corresponds to the axial direction of the mould.

3. Experimental results

3.1 Initial geometry of the specimens

The initial geometry of the specimens was established using a high precision 3D co-ordinate-measuring machine (BN710), equipped with a 40-mm long needle with 2-mm diameter ball. All measurements were carried out in a temperature-controlled room (20⁰ C). Samples were left for 1 hour in the CMM environment before taking the measurements, to minimise possible effects of temperature gradients. The measurements were taken at 3 sections along the length of each L-shape specimen and at 16 sections along the length of the U-channel. Most of the L-shape specimens exhibit a small amount of arm bowing. The angle between the arms was taken as being the angle between lines drawn from the end of each arm to the end of the radius, to take account of the bowing.

3.2 The effect of arm length on the initial value of the spring-in angle.

The effect of the sample arm length on the spring-in angle was investigated using the 4 L-shape specimens prepared with varying arm length. The specimens were cured at the same time on the aluminium tool according to the procedures presented in 2.1. It was found that the spring-in angle is getting smaller for the specimens with longer arms as illustrated in figure 4.

Fig 4. The effect of arm length on the value of the spring-in angle

The results of this experiment can be explained by assuming the presence of an interaction between the component and the aluminium mould. The tool-part interaction phenomenon occurs when the thermal expansion of the tool is greater than that of the laminate. As the pressure and temperature are applied in the autoclave the surface material is put into tension due to shear, which arises at the interface of the expanding tool and the laminate. Due to the low shear modulus of the resin at the early stages of the curing process the plies distant from the tooling are not loaded to the same extent as those close to the tool-part interface. This results in a non-uniform stress distribution through the thickness of the laminate. The stress gradient is locked in to the component as soon as the resin vitrifies. At the end of the process, when the part is removed from the tool, the stresses are relieved and the laminate distorts. In the case of moulding on female tooling, the gradient of locked-in stresses will tend to reduce spring-in. Assuming that the amount of stress locked in depends on the length, it is expected that specimens with long arms will exhibit a greater reduction in spring-in angle.

3.3 Experiments performed on the U-channel

3.3.1 Variation in the value of the initial spring-in angle along the length of the U-channel

Investigation of the point-to-point variation in the value of the spring-in angle was performed on the U-channel component denoted as UL1. The geometry of the sample was established using the CMM machine. Then both arms of the U-channel were slit in 7 places, with equal spacing of 60 mm, as shown in fig 5, to release the constraint effect from neighbouring parts. After slitting the sample the CMM measurements were repeated. The comparison between the spring-in angle values before and after slitting is illustrated in fig. 6 and 7.

Fig 5. Positions of the slits along the U-channel specimen

Fig 6. Variation in the initial spring-in angle after introducing slits r=16

Fig 7. Variation in the initial spring-in angle after introducing slits r=30

It can be seen that after introducing slits the spring-in angle for both 16 and 30-mm radius increases at the opposite ends of the channel as shown in fig 6 and 7. It was necessary to perform further experiments to investigate the source of this variation.

3.3.2 The variation in the thermoelastic spring-in angle along the length of the U-channel

A set of experiments was conducted to investigate the effect of a temperature excursion on the change of the enclosed angle along the length of the U-channel. For the purpose of the experiment the component was placed in an oven where a temperature change of 120 °C was applied. The specimen was supported at one point only. A laser measurement technique was used to measure the amount of thermoelastic spring-in. There was a mirror attached at the point of fixation to provide information about jig movements. The thermoelastic response of the channel was measured at 8 positions along each arm, fig.8. The values of spring-in angles measured at various positions on both sides of the U-channel are listed in table 3 and 4.

Fig 8. Experimental measurements of the thermoelastic spring-in angle.

Table 3. Variation in the thermoelastic spring-in angle along the length of the U-channel component
r= 30 mm

Position along the length	Thermoelastic spring-in (degrees)	Accuracy of the measurement	Change of the temperature:	Slope °/C ⁰
1	0.44	± 0.02	120	0.0037
2	0.47	± 0.02	120	0.0039
3	0.45	± 0.02	120	0.0038
4	0.45	± 0.02	120	0.0038
5	0.46	± 0.02	120	0.0038
6	0.48	± 0.02	120	0.0040
7	0.47	± 0.02	120	0.0039
8	0.45	± 0.02	120	0.0038

Table 4. Variation in the thermoelastic spring-in angle along the length of the U-channel component
r= 16 mm

Position along the length	Thermoelastic spring-in (degrees)	Accuracy of the measurement	Change of the temperature:	Slope $^{\circ}/C^{\circ}$
1	0.46	± 0.02	120	0.0038
2	0.48	± 0.02	120	0.0040
3	0.47	± 0.02	120	0.0039
4	0.46	± 0.02	120	0.0038
5	0.44	± 0.02	120	0.0037
6	0.45	± 0.02	120	0.0038
7	0.46	± 0.02	120	0.0038
8	0.48	± 0.02	120	0.0040

It can be seen that that the variation in the response due to applied temperature is very small and mostly falls within the limits of measurement accuracy. There is almost no difference in the thermoelastic response between 16 and 30-mm radii.

3.3.3 Discussion of the results

These results show that the difference of the spring-in before and after slitting was caused by a non-thermal effect. A possible explanation of this phenomenon can be given in terms of tool-part interaction by assuming that the amount of stress locked in the fibres depends on the fibre length. The tensile stress locked in the outer ply of the 'L' or 'U' shape component should decrease the spring-in angle. In the area where the length of the fibre is constant the amount of tool strain locked in the fibres should be constant, and so should be the value of the spring-in angle. Fibre paths of the surface ply are shown schematically in fig.9. The dashed lines indicate the area of shortest fibres. It was expected that the value of the spring-in angle in this region would be higher (less tensile stress in the outer ply).

Fig 9. Unfolded 1 ply of the u-channel (tool ply)

This explanation matches the experimental results, however a better understanding of the tool-part interaction and compaction mechanisms is needed to validate this hypothesis.

3.4 Experiments performed on the U-channel web

The beam web was essentially flat when measured by CMM as a whole beam. An experiment was carried out to investigate the geometry of the beam web only. For the purpose of the experiment the web of the component was cut out using a diamond saw figure 10. A considerable curvature could be observed when the radius and arm elements were removed,

as illustrated in fig. 11 and 12 respectively. A small increase in the amount of twist was measured as illustrated in fig.13. The thermoelastic tests performed on the web-only indicate that non-thermoelastic effects cause a major part of bowing and twist.

Fig.10 Schematic picture of the U-channel, showing web cut out along dashed lines.

Fig 11. Longitudinal bowing of the web (away from the tool)

Fig 12. Bowing of the web in the transverse direction (web bows away from the tool)

Fig.13 Twist measured along the U-channel web

The total amount of twist in both cases is very similar. It can be seen that the rate of twist for the web only decreases at the edges. Most of the twist as well as the transverse web bowing occur in the centre of the U-channel web. Assuming the presence of tool-part interaction the highest tensile stress is expected in the area of longest fibres that stay in touch with the expanding tool. The position of this place is shown in fig 13.

Fig 13. Fibre paths of the outer 45-degree ply

4 Conclusions

An experimental activity was performed to give a better understanding of process-induced distortions occurring in L-shape and U-channel components. The influence of sample arm length on the initial value of spring-in angle was examined. It was found that increasing the sample arm length decreases the spring-in angle.

Investigation of the point-to-point variation in the value of the spring-in angle was performed on the long U-shape component. A laser measurement technique was used to examine the response of the component due to applied temperature. It was shown that the variation in the thermoelastic response along the component is very small and in most cases

within the error of the measurement. It was shown there is almost no difference in the thermoelastic response between 16 and 30 mm radius. The varying length of the fibres that stay in contact with the tool might cause the variation in the value of the initial spring-in.

Whilst the beam web was essentially flat when measured by CMM as a whole beam, it showed a considerable curvature when the radius and arm elements were removed. The geometry of the beam as made is clearly contributing to its geometrical stability, the converse of which is that there must be locked-in residual stress in the component as made.

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